

Bioassay: The amine hydrochlorides were screened *in vitro* for amoebicidal activity against axenically grown *E. histolytica*. Their activity is reported in the Table 1. The substituted β -phenylethylamines are more active than the corresponding α -phenylethylamines and the 2-ethoxy-4-methoxy compounds more than the corresponding 2,4-dimethoxy compounds.

TABLE 1— α AND β -(2-ETHOXY-4-METHOXY-5-ALKYLPHENYL)ETHYLAMINE HYDROCHLORIDES AND THEIR AMOEBICIDAL ACTIVITY

Compound	R	m.p.	% Found (Calcd.)			Amoebicidal activity μ g/ml (min. inhib conc)
			O	H	N	
IVa	Et	203-10°	60.10 (60.19)	8.41 (8.48)	5.32 (5.39)	NA ⁺
IVb	<i>n</i> -Pr	194°	61.36 (61.42)	8.72 (8.77)	5.06 (5.12)	500
IVc	<i>n</i> -Bu	180°	62.56 (62.61)	9.02 (9.01)	4.83 (4.87)	500
VIIa	Et	218°	60.14 (60.19)	8.46 (8.48)	5.43 (5.39)	250
VIIb	<i>n</i> -Pr	212-3°	61.40 (61.43)	8.76 (8.77)	5.04 (5.12)	125
VIIc	<i>n</i> -Bu	155-6°	62.73 (62.61)	9.10 (9.03)	4.86 (4.87)	62.5

* NA = Non-active.

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Synthesis of Steroidal Spirothiazolidinones : Reaction of 5 α -Cholestane-3,6-dione with β -Mercaptoacetic Acid

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SPIROTHIAZOLIDINONES have been reported to have pharmacological activities such as anaesthetic¹, antibiotic² and amoebicidal³. These observations prompted us to undertake the synthesis of steroidal spirothiazolidinones⁴. This note

is concerned with the reaction of 5 α -cholestane-3,6-dione(I) with β -mercaptoacetic acid (BF₃-etherate as catalyst) which afforded isomeric steroidal spirothiazolidinones, S-spiro(5 α -cholestan-6-one-3,2')thiazolidinone-4'(II) and R-spiro(5 α -cholestan-6-one-3,2')thiazolidinone-4'(III). The structure of these compounds was established on the basis of ¹H nmr data.

Experimental

The dione (I)⁵ (1.50 g), β -mercaptoacetic acid (3.4 g, 10 mole excess), ammonium carbonate (3.6 g) in dry benzene (100 ml) was refluxed for 32 hr in Dean and Stark apparatus. At the end of the reaction, the benzene solution was washed with water, 1N sodium hydroxide solution and water and dried over anhydrous sodium sulphate. The solvent was removed under reduced pressure and chromatographed over silica gel (30.0 g). Elution with benzene-ether (8 : 1) furnished the compound (II) (0.37 g), m.p. 262°; Found: C, 73.4; H, 9.88; N, 2.93; S, 6.73. C₂₉H₄₇NO₂S requires C, 73.57; H, 9.93; N, 2.96; S, 6.76%. IR: $\nu_{\max}$ 3140, 3060

cm⁻¹ (—NH—), 1710 (—C—), 1690 (—NH—C—), 1420

cm⁻¹ (—CN), ¹H nmr: δ 8.10 brs (—NH—C—), 3.63 s (—C—CH₂—S—), 0.92 (C₁₀—CH₃), 0.70 (C₁₈—CH₃), 0.83 and 0.78 (other methyl protons).

Further elution with benzene-ether (6 : 1) yielded (III), recrystallized from light petroleum (0.45 g), m.p. 295°; Found: C, 73.41; H, 9.89; N, 2.43; S, 6.74. C₂₉H₄₇NO₂S requires C, 73.57; H, 9.93; N,

2.96; S, 6.76%. IR: $\nu_{\max}$ 3140, 3060 (—NH—C—), 1710 (—C—), 1690 (—NH—C—), 1429 cm⁻¹ (—CN)

¹H nmr δ 8.10 br (—NH—C—), 3.53 s (—C—CH₂—S), 0.92 (C₁₀—CH₃), 0.70 (C₁₈—CH₃), 0.83 and 0.78 (other methyl protons).

Results and Discussion

The compounds (II) and (III) analysed for C₂₉H₄₇NO₂S are isomeric. The ir spectra of (II)

and (III) exhibited a strong band at 1710 cm^{-1} for an isolated carbonyl group. It is a general observation in these reactions that the 3-oxo group is preferably more reactive than the 6-oxo groups⁶. Therefore the strong band at 1710 cm^{-1} is assigned

to $-\overset{\text{O}}{\parallel}{\text{C}}6-$ in compounds (II) and (III). The configuration at spirane carbon at C3 in compounds (II) and (III) was determined by ^1H nmr values. It has been found that in the case of isomer containing axial $\text{C}-\overset{\text{O}}{\parallel}{\text{N}}$ bond, ring methylene protons

($-\text{S}-\underset{\text{Spirane}}{\text{CH}_2}-\overset{\text{O}}{\parallel}{\text{C}}-$) signal is shifted downfield by $\delta 0.04-0.10$ ppm as compared to methylene protons signal where $\text{C}-\overset{\text{O}}{\parallel}{\text{N}}$ bond is equatorial⁷. Com-

parison of the ^1H nmr values for ring methylene protons in compounds (II) and (III) confirmed that C3- $\overset{\text{O}}{\parallel}{\text{N}}$ bond is axial in (II) and equatorial in (III).

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Girinimbine and Koenimbine from *Murraya exotica* Linn.

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IN continuation of the investigation on *Murraya exotica* Linn. in our laboratory, from which coumarins¹⁻⁵, carbazoles⁶, flavonoids^{7,8} were reported, we now report two carbazoles, koenimbine (I) $\text{C}_{19}\text{H}_{15}\text{NO}$ and girinimbine (II) $\text{C}_{19}\text{H}_{17}\text{NO}$ from the same plant.

(I)

(II)

The alkaloids were obtained from the neutral fraction of the petroleum ether ($60-80^\circ$) extract of the stem bark of *M. exotica* on chromatography over alumina and characterised by ir and uv spectral data and also by direct comparison with authentic samples.

Though the yield of the first carbazole (I) is very low, the isolation and identification of koenimbine and girinimbine from *M. exotica* Linn. (a member of the genus *Murraya*) is important from taxonomic standpoint.

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Phenyl Hydrazine-N-Dithiocarbamate : A New Gravimetric Reagent for the Determination and Separation of Copper(II) and Nickel(II)

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ALTHOUGH a lot of work has been carried out on dithiocarbamates and on their analytical¹⁻⁷ applications, phenyl hydrazine-N-dithiocarbamate has not been used in analytical field. Phenyl hydrazine-N-dithiocarbamate has been employed as a new gravimetric reagent for the separation and

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